

ASSESSMENT OF THE KNOWLEDGE AND PERSPECTIVE OF INFECTIOUS DISEASE
PREVENTION AND CONTROL AMONGST NURSING STUDENTS

ABSTRACT

Background: Infection prevention and control (IPC) is a practical, evidence-based approach which prevents patients and health workers from being harmed by avoidable infections. Infectious diseases creates an enormous burden on the economy and individuals by prolonging their stay in hospitals. It is essential that no patient gets an infection while receiving healthcare and as such necessary to access the knowledge and perspective of nursing students on infectious disease prevention and control. This study aimed at gathering information from KNUST nursing students on their knowledge and perspective of infectious and disease prevention.

Methods: Based on the research question a questionnaire was developed and distributed across social media platforms to KNUST nursing students. Respondents were only allowed to answer once and a period of two weeks was used to collect the responses. The questionnaires were sent to nursing students both on and off campus. The data was captured and analyzed

Results: All the respondents knew about infectious disease prevention and control. The majority of the students 95% and 77.2% had their knowledge from lecturers and hospital staff respectively. About 93% had detailed understanding of IPC. About 95%he students were aware about IPC method hand hygiene, 94.1% knew about vaccination and use of PPEs, 93.1% knew about immunization,

cleaning and disinfection and sterile instruments and devices and 86.1% knew about safe injection practices. About 92% of the students agree that their program creates enough awareness about IPC and 89% had received training on IPC. When asked about the policies of IPC 69.3% of the respondents knew about the Ghana National policies of IPC, 91% had come across different guidelines on the ward while 78% responded that the guidelines are being diligently followed.

Conclusion: The nursing students had better knowledge and attitudes towards IPC. This study has majority of the student nursing population of KNUST were well informed on IPC practices and its application in the health system

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

An infectious disease is described as a condition brought on by a virus, a bacteria, fungi or parasite and contracted by a vulnerable host from an infected person, animal, inanimate item, or both. The tremendous global burden of disease caused by infectious diseases, which disproportionately affect vulnerable communities, has an impact on global public health systems and economies. More than 9 million people died and over 45 million years were lost to incapacity as a result of infectious diseases in 2013. (Naghavi et al., 2015). Tuberculosis (TB), diarrheal diseases, lower respiratory tract infections, malaria, and HIV/AIDS are among the top causes of overall global mortality (Vos et al., 2015). Emerging infectious diseases are illnesses that have just surfaced (like Middle East Respiratory Syndrome) or that have long existed but are now spreading quickly across large geographic areas (like extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis (XDR TB) and Zika virus). (Morse, 1995).

According to the WHO, infection prevention and control (IPC) is a practical, evidence-based approach which prevents patients and health workers from being harmed by avoidable infection and as a result of antimicrobial resistance. The improvements in cleanliness, efficient use of vaccines, and the introduction and use of particular therapies are the main causes of the improvements in the control of infectious illnesses (Hinman, 1998). Healthcare environments, where there is a significantly higher risk of infection for patients, are particularly crucial for the prevention and control of infectious diseases. Therefore, it is crucial that students pursuing health-related education have the relevant knowledge and viewpoints about infectious illnesses, their prevention, and control.

The outcome of an infection brought on by an infectious agent depends on the dynamic interaction between inherent host factors influencing susceptibility to infection and disease and agent factors influencing infectivity, pathogenicity, and virulence.. Extrinsic determinants of host vulnerability to exposure include environmental factors and both physical and social behavioral. Living parasites (helminths or protozoa), fungus, bacteria, or inanimate viruses or prions are all examples of infectious agents. The likelihood of a host being exposed to one of these agents is determined by environmental conditions, and the course of the exposure is determined by the interactions between the agent and the host. Infection, illness, healing, or death are only a few of the stages in the cascade of interactions between an agent and a host.

1.2 Problem Statement

Infectious diseases create an enormous burden on the economy and individuals by prolonging their stay in hospitals. It is essential that no patient gets an infection while receiving healthcare and as such necessary to access the knowledge and perspective of nursing students on infectious disease prevention and control

1.3 Justification

Nurses make a large portion of healthcare workers in the Hospital hence can be a great source of the spread of infectious diseases. It is therefore necessary to access the perspective and knowledge of nursing students on Infectious disease prevention and control and make any necessary intervention, as they will be the next generation hospital staff to help reduce the spread of infectious diseases

1.4 Research question

Assessment of the knowledge and perspective of infectious disease prevention and control amongst nursing students

1.5 Aim

To assess the knowledge on infectious disease control and prevention amongst Nursing students in KNUST.

1.6 Objectives

1. To assess the understanding of infection prevention control by nursing students.
2. To find out what protection protocol they have in place to prevent infections.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

The health and safety of both those who seek out health services and those who provide them are impacted by infection prevention and control (IPC), a component of all health systems that is relevant on a global scale. As a result, the majority of healthcare systems worldwide may still connect to it as a universal healthcare concern. It includes the challenging duty of preventing and controlling hospital acquired infections (HCAIs), monitoring prevalent and newly emerging infectious diseases, and responding to catastrophes' aftereffects.

The global impact of HCAIs is difficult to determine, and the findings from various research are inconsistent. According to reports, 5 to 10% of individuals admitted to acute healthcare institutions develop an HCAI, and around 1.7 million people do so while undergoing treatment. This leads to more than 98,000 fatalities each year. According to research conducted in both Europe and the USA, there are an estimated 2.6 million new cases of HCAIs each year, with the incidence density of these infections ranging from 13.0 to 20.3 episodes per 1,000 patient-days. Although there is a lack of data on HCAIs in low income nations, it is assumed that the rate is high for obvious reasons. Because of the overcrowding in medical facilities, patients waiting to be treated for other illnesses may contract respiratory infections. Despite the fact that well-planned and meticulously implemented IPC programs reduce morbidity, prevent mortality, and save money, they are not widely used in settings with limited resources, and IPC standards vary greatly. Eight core elements for an IPC program are provided by the WHO's guidelines for IPC readiness at both the national and facility levels. These elements can be modified or adopted to fit all facilities in various environmental and financial contexts while maintaining the core elements and scientific rigor. Additionally, in 2015, the Ghana Ministry of Health updated its IPC policy and guidelines for national, regional, and facility level,

which are intended to guide all IPC activity in the nation's healthcare facilities. Recent international public health crises, such as the Middle Eastern respiratory syndrome coronavirus and the West African Ebola virus disease epidemics, exposed weaknesses in the IPC practices used by the affected nations. COVID-19 infection and transmission within hospitals have previously been widely documented as being extremely high.

IPC is a realistic, evidence-based strategy that safeguards patients and healthcare professionals from preventable infections and antibiotic resistance. (WHO)

An infectious disease is said to be caused by a mix of elements including the agent (pathogen), the host, and the environment according to the epidemiological triad (Snieszko, 1974). Infectious agents can include nonliving viruses or prions as well as living parasites (helminths or protozoa), fungus, or bacteria. If a host is exposed to one of these agents, exposure is determined by environmental conditions, and the outcome of the exposure is determined by interactions between the agent and host. Interactions between agents and hosts occur in a series of stages that include infection, disease, recovery, and death. Infection recovery can be complete (agent elimination) or incomplete. Incomplete recovery can result in both chronic and latent infections. Chronic infections are distinguished by the continued presence of an infectious agent. Latent infections, on the other hand, are distinguished by an agent that can remain dormant in host cells before being reactivated. For example, the varicella zoster virus, which causes chicken pox, can reactivate many years after a primary infection to cause shingles. Latent infections are significant in terms of public health because they serve as silent reservoirs of infectious agents for future transmission.

The result of an infection caused by an infectious agent depends on the dynamic interaction between the intrinsic host factors of susceptibility to infection and disease and the agent determinants of

infectivity, pathogenicity, and virulence (Figure 2(b)). Physical and social behavioral environmental variables are extrinsic determinants of host susceptibility to exposure. The possibility that an agent may infect a host if it is exposed to the agent is known as its infectiousness.. Pathogenicity refers to an agent's ability to cause disease when infected, whereas virulence refers to the likelihood of causing severe disease among those who have disease. Virulence is a reflection of an infectious agent's structural and/or biochemical properties.

Particularly, some infectious agents' virulence is caused by the production of toxins (endotoxins and/or exotoxins), such as the cholera toxin, which causes profuse watery diarrhea. Some exotoxins, such as staphylococcal enterotoxins that can cause foodborne diseases, cause disease independently of infection. Agent properties can be measured in a variety of ways. Infectivity is frequently measured in terms of infectious dose 50 (ID 50), which is the amount of agent required to infect 50% of a given host population. The ID50 for *Shigella dysenteriae* ranges from 10 organisms to 10⁶-10¹¹ for *Vibrio cholerae* (Gama et al., 2012; FDA, 2012).The attack rate, or the number of exposed individuals who develop disease, can be used to determine infectivity and pathogenicity (as it may be difficult to determine if someone has been infected if they do not have outward manifestations of disease). The case fatality rate or proportion of diseased individuals who die from the disease is frequently used to assess virulence.

Numerous host characteristics that affect an individual's susceptibility to infection and disease play a function in determining the outcome of an infectious agent exposure. Susceptibility is the term for an exposed person's (or a group of people's) biological makeup-based capacity to limit or resist sickness or infection. Susceptibility is influenced by innate, genetic variables as well as learned factors such as acquired immunity from vaccination or specific exposure. Sickle cell trait carriers' malaria resistance demonstrates how genetics can affect an individual's vulnerability to infectious disease. (Aidoo et al.,

2002). Extremes of age, stress, pregnancy, nutritional status, and underlying diseases all influence susceptibility. These latter factors, as demonstrated by immunologically naive infant populations, aging populations experiencing immune senescence, and immunocompromised HIV/AIDS patients, can impact immunity to infection. The first host barriers to infection are mechanical and chemical surface barriers such as the skin, the flushing action of tears, and the trapping action of mucus. Wound infection and secondary sepsis, for example, are serious complications of severe burns that destroy the skin's barrier to microbial entry. Bactericidal properties of lysozyme, which is secreted in saliva, tears, milk, sweat, and mucus, and gastric acid, and vaginal acid, which is microbicidal for many agents of sexually transmitted infections (STIs). Microbiome-resident bacteria (also known as commensal bacteria or normal flora) can provide host protection by utilizing available nutrients and space to keep pathogenic bacteria at bay.

Innate and adaptive immune responses are important components of the host's response to infectious agents. Each of these responses is carried out by cells of a different hematopoietic stem cell lineage: the myeloid lineage produces innate immune cells (e.g., neutrophils, macrophages, dendritic cells), while the lymphoid lineage produces adaptive immune cells (e.g., T cells, B cells). The innate immune response is a nonspecific, immediate response to a wide range of pathogens. The adaptive immune response, on the other hand, is initiated over a period of 3-4 days, recognizes specific pathogens, and is divided into two branches: (1) T cell-mediated immunity (also known as cell-mediated immunity) and (2) B cell-mediated immunity (a.k.a. humoral or antibody-mediated immunity). In addition, the innate and adaptive responses differ in that the latter has memory while the former does not. As a result of adaptive immune memory, if an infectious agent tries to infect a host again, pathogen-specific memory T cells, memory B cells, and antibodies mount a secondary

immune response that is much faster and more intense than the initial, primary response, and thus better able to inhibit infection and disease. Immune memory serves as the foundation for the use of vaccines, which are administered in an attempt to stimulate an individual's adaptive immune system to generate pathogen-specific immune memory. It should be noted that in some cases, the immune system's response to an infectious agent can contribute to disease progression. Immunopathology, for example, is thought to be responsible for the severe acute disease that can occur after infection with a dengue virus that is serotypically distinct from the virus that caused the initial dengue infection (Screaton et al., 2015). Physical, social, behavioral, cultural, political, and economic factors are all environmental determinants of infectious disease vulnerability. In some cases, environmental factors increase the likelihood of being exposed to an infectious agent. Following an earthquake, for example, environmental disruption can increase the risk of exposure to *Clostridium tetani* and result in host traumatic injuries that serve as entry points for the bacterium. Environmental factors that promote vulnerability can also increase susceptibility to infection by inducing physiological changes in a person. A child living in a resource-poor setting, for example, who is susceptible to malnutrition, may be at increased risk of infection due to malnutrition-induced immunosuppression.

Many infectious diseases have the peculiar property that exposure to specific infectious agents can have effects on other people because a sick person can act as a source of exposure. Some pathogens—like STI agents—transmit to other individuals directly, whereas others—like agents of vectorborne disease (VBD)—transmit to people indirectly. It is crucial to get an accurate diagnosis of infectious diseases in order to treat patients appropriately and carry out preventative and control surveillance efforts. Sensitivity and specificity are two crucial factors that should be taken into account for any diagnostic test that is used. Sensitivity describes a test's capacity to accurately identify people who are infected with an agent (or who are "positive in illness"). A very sensitive test

will have fewer false negative results and is more likely to detect those who have the disease (and perhaps some who do not). Specificity is a test's capacity to correctly identify people who are not infected by a certain agent (i.e., are "negative in health"); high specificity suggests a low number of false positive results. Frequently, confirmatory tests are more focused whereas screening tests are more sensitive (to detect any potential instances) (to rule out false-positive screening tests). The classification of infectious disease preventive activities as primary, secondary, or tertiary is based on the traditional model of Leavell and Clark (1965). To protect people from infection and disease, primary prevention takes place during the predisease stage. For instance, measles vaccination programs seek to reduce susceptibility after exposure. Secondary prevention aims to stop an infection in its early, frequently asymptomatic phases in order to stop illness development or lessen the severity of it. These actions are crucial for both enhancing the prognosis of individual cases and limiting the spread of infectious agents. For instance, active surveillance and screening are interventions for secondary prevention of hepatitis C in populations of injecting drug users, as well as early diagnosis and treatment (Miller and Dillon, 2015). Tertiary prevention concentrates on those with disease with the aim of limiting impact, for instance, through therapies that slow the advancement of the disease, improve functionality, and improve quality of life. In general, primary and secondary prevention strategies that lessen the chance of exposure to an infectious agent and build host resistance to infection are the main emphasis of public health efforts to manage infectious illnesses. As stated by the 1997 Dahlem Workshop on the Eradication of Infectious Diseases, the goal of these actions may go beyond disease control in order to achieve elimination and eradication objectives. (Dowdle, 1998; Box 1).

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study design and study population

To assess the knowledge and perspective of nursing students in KNUST in this study, a descriptive cross-sectional study design was used and data was collected through convenient sampling. The target population comprised undergraduate nursing students enrolled in the Faculty of Nursing. Questionnaires were developed and distributed electronically to KNUST nursing students. Respondents were allowed to answer once and a period of two weeks was used to collect the responses.

3.2 Survey instrument

The questionnaire was developed following a review of relevant literature. It consisted of three parts that assessed respondents' year of study, their knowledge of IPC and the IPC policies implemented in their clinical practice. The instrument included one question on the year of study, six questions assessing IPC knowledge, and three questions evaluating the IPC policies used in practice

3.3 Data handling and analysis

Data collected through Google Forms were exported into GraphPad Prism for analysis. After cleaning and organizing the dataset, descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and graphical summaries were generated to describe the key findings.

3.4 Inclusion criteria

The study involved all students from the Faculty of Nursing KNUST.

3.5 Exclusion criteria

Students from other universities and nursing or midwifery training institutions were excluded from the study.

3.6 Ethical considerations

The purpose of the study was clearly explained to all respondents before participation. Participation was voluntary, and anonymity of responses was ensured. No identifying information was collected, and all data were used solely for academic purposes. Although formal ethical approval was not sought, the study adhered to basic ethical principles of confidentiality and informed consent.

3.7 Limitation of the study

First, because the questionnaire was self-administered, the responses may be subject to recall bias and social desirability bias. The relatively small sample size, due to time constraints, may also limit the statistical strength and generalization of the findings. Additionally, no regression or multivariate analysis was conducted, preventing the control of potential confounding variables. Finally, as the study focused solely on nursing and midwifery students from KNUST, the results may not be representative of other student populations or healthcare settings in Ghana.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

4.1 Demographic Data of Respondent

The total number of responses received for the study was 102 respondents. Of the respondents, 10.1% were first-year students, 22.2% were second-year students, 54.5% were third-year students, and 13.1% were fourth-year students. Table 1 shows the demographic of the respondents.

Table 1 Demographics of respondents

Year of study	Frequency (n)	Percentages (%)
First	10	10.1
Second	22	22.2
Third	54	54.5
Fourth	13	13.1

Figure 1 Demographics of respondents

4.2 Knowledge about Infectious Prevention and Control

The respondents' knowledge and awareness of infection prevention and control (IPC) are summarized in Table 2. Most KNUST nursing students were aware of IPC and knew its key methods, with lecturers and hospital staff as the main information sources. While training and program awareness were high, safe injection practices and hands-on training showed slight gaps, highlighting areas for improvement.

Table 2 Knowledge about infectious disease prevention and control

Question		Frequency (n)	Percentages (%)
Have you heard about IPC	Yes	102	100%
	no	0	0%
The source of information about IPC	Lecturers	96	94.1%
	Hospital Staff	78	76.5%
	Internet	50	49.0%
	Fliers/Posters	35	34.3%
	Friends	32	31.4%
	Family	29	28.4%
	Don't know	2	2.0%
Do you know what IPC entails	Yes	93	91.2%
	No	7	6.9%
Which methods of IPC	Hand hygiene	96	94.1%

have you heard of	Vaccination	95	93.1%
	Use of PPEs	95	93.1%
	Immunization	94	92.2%
	Cleaning and disinfection	94	92.2%
	Sterile instruments and devices	94	92.2%
	Safe injection practices	87	85.3%
Does your program provide IPC awareness	Yes	92	90.2%
	No	8	7.8%
Have you received any form of training on IPC	Yes	90	88.2%
	No	11	10.8%

Figure 2 Source of information of Respondents

Figure 3 Methods of IPC

4.3 Policies and Guidelines on Infectious Disease Prevention and Control in Hospital Settings

The table below shows the knowledge students have about the guidelines and policies in the health care settings and how these guidelines and policies are being used.

Table 3 Knowledge about Policies and Guidelines on Infectious Disease Prevention and Control in Hospital Settings

Question		Frequency (n)	Percentages (%)
Have you heard about the Ghana National	Yes	70	68.6%
Policy on IPC in a hospital setting	No	32	31.4%
Throughout your internship experience have	Yes	91	89.2%
you come across any policy or guideline on IPC	No	9	8.8%
If yes, are these policies and guidelines	Yes	78	76.5%
diligently followed by nursing staff	No	22	21.6%

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION

Infectious diseases are a major problem for patients and health workers, making their prevention a top priority for healthcare systems. Healthcare associated infections can result in reduced quality of life or even reduce the life expectancy of the infected person, as well as incur considerable costs in the long term (Alhumaid et al., 2021). In Ghana, nurses constitute the largest proportion of hospital workers, with the nurse to patient ratio being 1:1000 while doctor to patient ratio is 1:10000 and pharmacist to patient ratio 1:13000, according to Ghanaweb. In light of this, we performed a study to assess the knowledge and perspectives of nursing students about infectious disease prevention and control and identify the measures in place to reduce infections.

From the study, it was identified that KNUST nursing students demonstrate a high level of awareness regarding infection prevention and control (IPC). Raising awareness is beneficial not only for patients and healthcare workers but also for the healthcare system and economy, as it helps reduce infection transmission and associated burdens. This is because most of the nurses will be conscious about the dangers of not practicing good IPC and benefit of IPC hence it will reduce the spread of infections and reduce the burden on them, patients and the economy. Additionally, the BSc Nursing program at KNUST provides adequate training on IPC. While awareness is important, formal training allows students to gain a deeper understanding through practical experience, better equipping them to implement IPC measures effectively.

One key finding from the study was that the Ghana National Policy on Infectious Disease prevention and Control is not consistently applied across all healthcare facilities. This is because while 68.6% of the students were aware of the National Policy, 89.2% of students knew about different guidelines

used by different hospitals. This gap may contribute to inconsistencies in infection control practices and could impose additional training burdens on healthcare organizations when nurses are transferred or newly employed.

Despite this, the study found that IPC guidelines and policies are generally followed in practice, with 76.5% of students reporting that nursing staff diligently adhere to these measures on the wards.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusion

From the study, it can be concluded that KNUST nursing students possessed adequate knowledge about infectious disease prevention and control, and that infection prevention guidelines and policies are generally implemented effectively on the wards. Awareness and training play key roles in equipping students to reduce the spread of infections.

6.2 Recommendations

Awareness campaigns on infectious disease prevention and control should be expanded beyond lecturers and hospital staff to include the internet, fliers/posters, friends, and family. This would help increase knowledge among students and raise public awareness about infection prevention. Efforts should be made to ensure the existing national IPC guidelines and policies are consistently implemented across all healthcare facilities. This could include regular training, monitoring adherence, and reinforcing the importance of these guidelines among healthcare workers and students.

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